

Enhanced Safe and Sustainable
coatings for supporting the Planet

NEWSLETTER

Issue 3, JUNE 2024

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Funded by the European Union under the GA no **101091842**.
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INTERVIEW WITH DR. FABIOLA BRUSCIOTTI FROM TECNALIA

Fabiola Brusciotti has a Doctoral degree in Engineering Science from Columbia University of the city New York (2006), in the department of Environmental Engineering, working on wet chemistry and metals removal from drinking water. Since then, she has been working as a researcher at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel first and the Instituto Superior Tecnico in Lisbon later, participating and coordinating projects dealing with surface and electrochemical characterization of organic/inorganic coatings for corrosion protection of aluminium and magnesium alloys.

She joined Tecnalia in 2012 as a Researcher and Project Manager in the Surface Engineering group, dealing with modification of surfaces with different functionalities, from corrosion protection, anti-fouling, hydrophobic surfaces, etc., for various sectors of application, such as aerospace, automotive and marine structures, among others. She presented her work in many international congresses devoted to electrochemistry and/or coatings of metals and she published several papers in international peer-reviewed journals.

1. Could you describe the role of TECNALIA within the project?

TECNALIA's role in PROPLANET is the technical coordination of the project, as well as of the development and optimization of PFAS-free and sustainable-by-design coatings. TECNALIA is monitoring the technical progress of the project with the support of the project coordinator, IDENER. The aim is ensuring a smooth flow of information among the technical partners for an efficient development of safe-and-sustainable-by-design (SSbD) coatings and a reliable application process.

On the technical side, TECNALIA is in charge of the development of coatings formulations for food-packaging machines and low-maintenance glass sectors. Both lines of coatings are being developed using the sol-gel technique and taking into account the specifications and requirements provided by the end users (REEPACK and PILKINGTON). Process optimization also takes into

account circularity and toxicity assessment as well as results of first-principle based models and simulations to evaluate the coatings performance.

2. How is the sol-gel technique employed in order to find PFAS-free coating solutions?

The sol-gel technique is a wet chemical method for the preparation of pure or mixed ceramic materials. It is a promising route that offers a vast range of opportunities for coating engineering due to the ability to synergistically combine inorganic and organic moieties that can be chemically bonded to form a hybrid material providing an array of properties.

Completely inorganic silicon precursors with four hydrolysable groups capable of hydrolyse and condense with four other silicon alkoxides can react with an acid or basic catalyst resulting in inorganic materials with increased durability, scratch resistance as well as

thermal and chemical resistance and adhesion to the metal substrate. The incorporation of metal alkoxides with organic functional groups into the coating matrix gives place to increased coating density and flexibility, improved mechanical properties, and when needed, thicker coatings. In addition, taking into consideration the organic functional group added to the hybrid network, the surface can be further functionalised to comply with a specific required property (e.g. anti-corrosion, hydrophobicity, etc.).

It is in this versatile matrix that suitable molecules will be chosen to substitute PFAS compounds, while providing comparable properties (i.e. hydro- and oleo-phobicity, thermal resistance, etc.) to the final product, depending on the specific application.

3. How do research and industrial partners collaborate in PROPLANET to ensure the practical application of its innovations?

The development of the project is based on a close

collaboration between the different partners, in particular the two centers in charge of the chemical development of the coatings formulation and process (NIC and TECNALIA), and the end-users (AITEK, PILKINGTON and REEPACK), who are providing specifications and requirements and will be in charge of the final validation of the results. This ensures that PROPLANET solutions would be scalable and easy and safe to manufacture.

In addition, other important aspects related to the industrial application of the processes are overseen by scientific and industrial partners through a SSbD approach, to ensure the circularity of the coatings, reduce their environmental impact and avoid any toxicological hazard. This will be also achieved with the implementation of mathematical and computational tools.

Overall, PROPLANET consortium is multidisciplinary, covering different expertise such as coating materials, multi-physical modelling, tool development, digitalization, open science, environmental, toxicological sciences, and economic aspects, in close cooperation between academia and industry.

OUR END APPLICATIONS

WE ARE TARGETING IN 3 INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

TEXTILES SECTOR TECHNICAL CLOTHES

Coatings for technical textiles presenting water/oil repellency.

FOOD SECTOR FOOD-PACKAGING MACHINE

Hybrid siloxane biobased coatings applied on plates for tray-sealer and/or thermoforming machines presenting non-stickness, anti-corrosion, thermal and mechanical stress stability.

LOW MAINTENANCE GLASS

Hybrid siloxane biobased coatings applied on low maintenance glass lamination (e.g. for shower doors, or car windows) with anti-soiling, and anti-reflective properties.

ATTENDANCE TO EVENTS

AITEX participated at the 49th AEQCT SIMPOSIUM -TEXTILE, SOLUTIONS AND OPPORTUNITIES, during 11/04/2024, in Terrassa – Barcelona, in Spain. AITEX presented PROPLANET concept on a Flash-Talk: “Solutions to reduce water consumption and presence of PFAS in textile finishing processes” (“Soluciones para la reducción del consumo de agua y la presencia de PFAS en procesos de acabado textil”).

[FIND OUT MORE ABOUT THE SYMPOSIUM](#)

AITEX was at the 18th Textile ETP Conference 2024 titled: Shaping New Horizons for the Textile Sector, held at Mechelen in Belgium between 14th and 15th of May 2024. This conference united industry leaders, experts, and innovators for two engaging days of discussions and insights, emphasizing sustainability, innovation, funding, and the future of the textile sector.

[FIND OUT MORE ABOUT THE CONFERENCE](#)

TECNALIA was at the International Trade Fair for Surface Technology held in Stuttgart, Germany between 4th and 6th June 2024. This fair provides a platform for companies in the surface technology sector to enhance productivity and efficiency, especially during economic downturns.

[FIND OUT MORE ABOUT THE FAIR](#)

ATTENDANCE TO EVENTS

NILU and NovaMechanics participated at the MaterialsWeek 2024 event, held at Crowne Plaza Hotel in Limassol, Cyprus between 17th and 21st of June 2024. This event (organised by NovaMechanics) aimed to unite the small and large research and Innovation communities that are propelling materials innovation across diverse value chains and industrial markets. NILU presented their poster on the Development of PFAS-free coatings in a safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) approach.

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

PROPLANET FEATURED IN OTHER CHANNELS

The PROPLANET consortium updates have been widely featured across multiple channels and events:

- TECNALIA organised an internal workshop on 19/04/2024. The aim of this internal workshop was to discuss about PFAS and the development of PFAS-free coatings finding applications in sectors such as low maintenance glass, food packaging machines and kitchenware, as validated within PROPLANET project and beyond. Check here:

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7186625394681274368>

NIC participated in the ISCRE 28 International Symposium on Chemical Reaction Engineering 2024, held from June 16th to 19th in Turku, Finland. This prestigious conference brought together leading experts and researchers in the field of chemical reaction engineering. NIC contributed to the discussions, sharing insights and advancements from PROPLANET, with a poster presentation as well, fostering valuable connections with peers from around the world.

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

- The PROPLANET project was announced in AITEX's magazine (no. 76) in May 2024. There the PFAS replacement opportunities in textiles were highlighted. Check it [here](#).

- The PROPLANET 12M consortium meeting hosted by TECNALIA in San Sebastian (Feb 20-21, 2024), Spain, was featured on EXELISIS' website and social media. HOLOSS announced its participation in the meeting to its network and further engaged its audience by reposting and sharing PROPLANET's post about the event. TECHNIALIA reposted PROPLANET's post about the meeting. Check [here](#).

- PROPLANET's official video was created during the first year of the project by EXELISIS, to raise awareness about innovative coatings on textiles, food packaging, and glass for a more sustainable planet. The video was also featured on EXELISIS' website. PROPLANET's post to its network regarding its official video, was reposted by HOLOSS and ECOSYSTEMEX. EXELISIS also created

PROPLANET's YouTube channel to showcase the videos created in the PROPLANET project. Check it [here](#).

- HOLOSS reposted PROPLANET's invitation to the first social media engagement streaming event. This event was organised by HOLOSS on 11th of December 2023 to share knowledge about: Tackling Pollutants, Protecting Health, and the Environment. HOLOSS also reposted PROPLANET's post about the completion of the aforementioned [event](#).

- HOLOSS created 3 infographic videos to help the audience dive into the world of PFAS-free, safe and sustainable by design coatings with exciting animations and simple explanations. The videos were showcased by PROPLANET in social media posts. PROPLANET's posts were reposted by HOLOSS and TECNALIA. Check out the video [here](#).

- PROPLANET dedicated a post about celebrating International Women's Day on 8th of March 2024. The post was reposted by UMA, HOLOSS, TECNALIA and NIC.

You may find the post [here](#).

- PROPLANET project was featured on the "Ugriznimo znanost" show, on RTV Slovenia where the project's partner NIC presented insights of the work done as part of PROPLANET's mission to replace PFAS, which are resistant to fats, oil, water, and heat, posing health hazards. PROPLANET's social media post about this show was reposted by NIC. You may find the show [here](#) in Slovenian.

- HOLOSS reposted PROPLANET's post about its participation at the 22nd International Sol-Gel Conference in Berlin (1st-6th Sept 2024) with the purpose of sharing insights on creative solutions and breakthroughs in sustainable coatings technology. Find out more [here](#).

- EXELISIS promoted the PROPLANET project at their booth in POLYMERS 2024 conference, held in Athens, Greece, between 28th-31st May 2024. This information was also shared through EXELISIS' [social media](#) and website.

- [PROPLANET's 18M consortium meeting](#), that took place on 10th-11th June, in Piraeus, Greece was shared on EXELISIS' social media and website and on TECNALIA's social media.

PROPLANET PUBLICATIONS

The first publication was announced by our partner NIC. It is titled “Unveiling PFAS-free Solutions for Hydrophobic and Oleophobic Textile Coatings” written by Verbič A. et al. This article discusses the widespread use and environmental impact of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in the textile industry.

The article emphasises the need to develop sustainable PFAS-free alternatives that can match the performance of traditional PFAS coatings. It outlines the challenges in creating these alternatives, such as maintaining durability, functionality, and compatibility with various textiles, while ensuring economic viability and minimal environmental impact.

The second article is titled “A template wizard for the cocreation of machine-readable data-reporting to harmonize the evaluation of (nano)materials” written by Jeliaskova N. et al. and published by our partner NILU. This article introduces a new tool designed to help researchers efficiently manage their experimental data. The tool, a template wizard, simplifies the process of creating templates for capturing data and metadata in a way that aligns with the FAIR principles. This user-friendly wizard generates templates that ensure machine-readable metadata, adhering to existing community standards and databases. It also includes an online validator to help researchers verify the accuracy and compliance of their templates.

These templates, which cover a range of nanosafety data including physicochemical characterization, hazard assessments, and exposure studies, are versatile enough to be adapted for fields like microplastics and advanced materials research. The article emphasised the importance of using standardised terminology and units to ensure data can be effectively reused and compared across different studies. By following guidelines and using harmonised terms, researchers can significantly improve data retrieval and the reliability of interlaboratory comparisons.

PROPLANET ZENODO COMMUNITY

A dedicated [PROPLANET Zenodo community](#) was created that will include all the newsletters, publications and open access reports of the PROPLANET project. [Zenodo](#), is an online general-purpose open repository built as part of the European OpenAIRE program operated by CERN. It enables researchers to submit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and other research-related digital artifacts . For each submission, a persistent Digital Object Identification (DOI) is generated, making the saved objects easily citable.

PROPLANET 18M CONSORTIUM MEETING AND REVIEW MEETING

We are excited to announce that the PROPLANET Project Month 18 Consortium Meeting was successfully held on June 10th and 11th in the vibrant city of Piraeus, Greece. The event was hosted by our esteemed partner NovaMechanics Ltd at the Alex, Monte Kastella hotel, marking a significant milestone in our project's journey.

The meeting demonstrated the outstanding progress made across various aspects of the PROPLANET project. Partners gathered to review progress, share key insights and plan for the project's future phases. The engaging discussions on coatings development, Sustainable Safe-by-Design (SSbD) principles, and sustainability aspects, were the highlight of this event, which set the stage for collaborative endeavours moving forward.

The first day concluded with a networking dinner, fostering cooperation and fortifying partnerships in Piraeus.

We deeply appreciate NovaMechanics Ltd for their gracious hospitality and organisational efforts in hosting this pivotal meeting. Their support has been instrumental in steering PROPLANET towards achieving its objectives as we prepare for the upcoming review meeting later this month.

Followingly, on June 20th, the review meeting of the PROPLANET project was held remotely. During this meeting, the consortium successfully presented all the advancements of its work during the first 18 months of the project to the Project officer and the Project Monitor.

PROPLANET VIDEOS

PROPLANET OFFICIAL VIDEO

Aiming to enhance dissemination, engage stakeholders and raise awareness of the project's objectives, accomplishments and impacts, EXELISIS produced the [PROPLANET official video](#). Released towards the end of the project's first year in 2023, the video aims to showcase the project's concept and results.

PROPLANET INFOGRAPHIC VIDEOS

To reach a broader audience, three additional infographic videos were created to help audiences without a scientific background understand the PROPLANET concept. These videos, produced by HOLOSS, are available on the [PROPLANET YouTube channel](#).

OUR CLUSTER

Throughout this period, PROPLANET has actively engaged with five additional projects dedicated to advancing innovative and sustainable coating formulations. For more information about BIO-SUSHY, Tornado, ZeroF, ESTELLA and IRISS projects visit [here](#).

PRESENTATION OF THE TORNADO PROJECT COORDINATOR TO THE PROPLANET CONSORTIUM

PROPLANET's 12M consortium meeting hosted by the project's coordinator TECNALIA, was held in San Sebastian, Spain between 20-21 February 2024. During this meeting TECNALIA presented the Tornado project to the consortium as part of PROPLANET's cluster.

THE 1ST CLUSTER KICK-OFF MEETING

The first No-PFAS cluster meeting was successfully completed. On May 14th, partners from BIO-SUSHY, ZEROF, PROPLANET, and TORNADO convened for this initial gathering. All projects share the common goal of developing PFA-free alternative solutions. It was wonderful to share our objectives, potential challenges, and future collaboration strategies within this community. Special thanks to BIO-SUSHY for organising the event.

MEET OUR LAST 5 MEMBERS OF OUR CONSORTIUM

* Find more of our consortium members in the next PROPLANET newsletter...

The **NSG Group** is one of the world's leading manufacturers of glass and glazing systems in three major business areas: Architectural Glass Products, Automotive and Technical Glass. NSG Group acquired the leading UK-based glass manufacturer **PILKINGTON** in June 2006.

REEPACK SRL is a manufacturer of packaging machinery and lines, mostly for food sector, healthcare, consumer goods, and industrial components.

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Ruka Innovation is a producer of antiviral & anti-microbial protective plastic films with expertise in standardisation protocols and roadmaps.

RINA is a company committed to simplifying complexities with a focus on energy transition, sustainability and digitisation. Their expertise in first-principles-based models and simulations to evaluate the performance are in the focus of the project.

The **University of Malaga** is a leading Spanish University and the team working under PROPLANET has worked deeply in mathematical models' simulation and multidisciplinary design optimisation.

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